

STUDY OF WIRELESS NETWORK SECURITY IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The rapid growth and deployment of these systems into a wide range of networks and for a wide variety of applications drives the need to support security solutions that meet the requirements of a wide variety of customers. In this paper attention has been focused on the security aspects of existing Wi-Fi (IEEE 802.11) wireless LAN systems. This paper will present a brief overview of the wireless protocols and technology, and then look at what's required to secure own wireless network to keep unauthorized users out of network. Wireless security can be broken into two parts: Authentication and Encryption. Authentication mechanisms can be used to identify a wireless client to an access point and vice-versa, while Encryption mechanisms ensure that it is not possible to intercept and decode data. For many years, MAC access control lists have been used for authentication, and 802.11 WEP has been used for encryption. Lastly, security precautions will be examined.

Key-Words: LAN, WPAN, WMAN, WEP.

1. INTRODUCTION

Wireless technologies in the simplest sense; enable one or more devices to communicate without physical connections. The devices simply need to be within a certain distance known as the range of the wireless network infrastructure or wireless peer to communicate.

Radio frequency transmissions are the means for transmitting data. Wireless technologies range from complex systems, such as cell phone networks and enterprise wireless local area networks to simple devices such as wireless keyboards, mice, microphones, etc.

There are many forms of wireless networks. A common way of categorizing wireless networks is to consider the relative range and complexity of each type of network. The major categories of wireless networking architectures are as follows:

1.1 Wireless personal area network (WPAN): a small-scale wireless network that requires little or no infrastructure and operates within a short range. A WPAN is typically used by a few devices in a single room instead of connecting the devices with cables.

1.2 Wireless local area networks (WLAN): are groups of wireless networking nodes within a limited geographic area, such as an office building or building campus, which is capable of radio communications. This is usually implemented as extensions to existing wired local area networks to enhanced user mobility.

1.3 Wireless metropolitan area networks (WMAN): can provide connectivity to users located in multiple facilities generally within a few miles. Many WMAN implementations provide wireless broadband access to customers in metropolitan areas.

1.4 Wireless wide area networks (WWAN) connect individuals and devices over large areas. WWANs are typically used for cellular voice and data communications, as well as satellite communications.

2. WIRELESS NETWORK COMPONENTS AND TOPOLOGIES

There are a number of wireless technologies and devices available in the today. An overview of each of the core components is wireless network security IEEE 802.11a/b/g follows:

2.1 Client Devices: Client devices in wireless networks, also referred to as stations, serve as wireless endpoint devices. Client devices enable end users to gain access and utilize resources provided by wireless networks.

Common examples of client devices are laptop computers, personal digital assistants, mobile phones, and other consumer electronic devices with wireless capabilities.

2.2 Access Points: An access point logically connects client devices to one another and provides access to the distribution system, if connected, which is typically an organization's enterprise wired network. Wireless access points provide users with a mobile capability by allowing users to freely move within an access point's coverage area while maintaining connectivity between the user's client device and the access point.

2.3 Wireless Bridges: A wireless bridge links two wired networks generally operating at two different physical locations. Bridges are often used to connect two buildings or two networks where a wired link is not feasible or cost efficient. Wireless bridges are similar to access points, but generally only serve to provide point-to-point wireless links

2.3 Base Stations: A base station or radio transceiver is similar to an access point, but serves a WMAN. A base station is typically a two-way radio installed at a fixed location to provide wireless access. A base station covers a much larger area than an IEEE 802.11 access point and

thus can serve significantly to more clients. The specific range and client support vary by base station vendor and technology.

Figure 1. Network Topologies

3. AUTHENTICATION

MAC authentication of wireless clients is supported by orinoco access points. The orinoco access point will determine whether the particular MAC address is valid by checking it against a database within the nonvolatile storage of the access point. It is a poor authentication mechanism because it is can be evaded, because authentication is unilateral. It can be evaded for two reasons.

First, software's are available in the market to change the MAC address of some 802.11 cards. Second, authentication is bounded to the hardware that a client is using and not to the identity of the client. Therefore, it could be possible to steal a legitimate client's PC and gain illegal access to a network. Unilateral authentication means that the access point authenticates the client, but the client does not authenticate the access point. This unilateral authentication is a problem because an unsuspecting client could associate to a rogue access point and begin passing network usernames and passwords through the illegitimate access point. This would allow hacker to capture the unsuspecting client's credentials to gain access to other network resources.

4. ENCRYPTION

Much attention has been paid in the recent years to the fact that Wired Equivalent Privacy (WEP) encryption, defined by 802.11 is not an industrial strength encryption protocol. WEP is still in general use today either because administrators are not concerned about hackers, or because the wireless network is secured by other means. Virtual Private Networking mechanisms (VPNs) are the most common means to secure wireless networks that are either using WEP encryption or no security at all. Many wireless administrators elect to forgo WEP altogether and use VPN software for encryption. This option is preferable for public wireless hotspot providers that are trying to attract as many users as possible by keeping client configuration as simple as possible. Hotspot customers use VPN software to connect to their company's network. The VPN option is also preferable to many enterprise administrators because VPN solutions offer the best commercially available encryption strength.

5. SECURITY ENHANCEMENTS

Many different methods to secure wireless networks exist today, each with their own caveats, while more are emerging over the horizon.

5.1 Explicit Client Restrictions: Typically, the Ethernet address, or MAC address, of the users wireless network interface card can be programmed into a wireless Access Point to allow access only from specific network interface cards. This mechanism is handy for a small wireless installation only. However, this method can quickly create enormous administration overhead, for the individual interface cards must be tracked, and the addresses of these cards must be programmed into each wireless Access Point where access is desired. Although this technique restricts access to only a few network cards, a crafty intruder could reprogram their wireless network interface card with an allowed address and gain access to the wireless network.

5.2 User Authentication: The user must first login to the network via this application before they can connect to the wireless network.

Administration tasks for this solution is fairly high, for the users login must appear in every wireless Access Point where access is desired, and yet another password must be remembered by the user. This authentication method provides a certain level of security, but is not without risks and caveats. In most cases, the user may set this password to the same password used for access to other systems, which would jeopardize other computing resources if the password were compromised.

Depending on the method used to send the password to the wireless Access Point, an attacker could capture the login sequence 'out of thin air', or possibly launch a brute-force password crack against the wireless Access Point, which essentially tries to continuously login by trying various password combinations until it "cracks" the password.

5.3 Network Naming: A Network Name, or SSID, may be assigned to a wireless network, and programmed into each wireless client. This Network Name is first verified when a wireless client attempts to connect to a wireless Access Point. If the name does not match, connectivity is rejected. Some administration responsibilities are required to program the Network Name into each wireless client upon the initial installation, and every time the Network Name is changed. Since this Network Name can be viewed in the client's network properties, and is transmitted over the wireless network in unencrypted form, an attacker can obtain it with little effort.

5.4 Wired Equivalent Privacy (WEP):

Recently, a method to encrypt the wireless data was introduced. Wired Equivalent Privacy (WEP) offers the ability to encrypt data utilizing either 40-bit or 128-bit encryption algorithms. The current WEP implementation utilizes a shared-key method, in which a 'password' is created and installed on every wireless device and wireless Access Point.

Data communications are encrypted and decrypted with this key. Attackers cannot easily obtain this key through packet capturing techniques, but instead rely on brute-force cracking of capture data streams, or other social-engineering methods. If this encryption key is compromised, an effort must be made to create a new encryption key and to configure each wireless client with the new key.

5.5 Emerging Standards: The IEEE has identified problems with each of the currently available wireless security mechanism. It has been working on documents to mitigate the risks and administration overhead associated with each technique, while ensuring operability with the majority of Wireless clients. These documents are the 802.11x and 802.11e standards. These documents discuss the ability to provide user-level authentication against popular authentication mechanisms utilized for Remote Access methods. Current wireless vendors are starting to adopt the methods described in these documents, and should be releasing products that utilize these methods later this year.

5.6 Firewalls/VPN: In a large wireless implementation, a firewall approach may be desired. Instead of having to create and maintain separate wireless authentication mechanisms, the wireless networks may be treated as one would treat access to the Internet.

The wireless network could be separated from the corporate network with a firewall, and existing VPN technologies could be used to gain access to business resources. This will help to ensure a seamless transition to the security imposed on the wireless network.

Using a wireless network in your home gives you the convenience of being able to use your computer virtually anywhere in your house — and still be able to connect to other computers on your network or access the Internet. However, if your wireless network is not secure, there are significant risks. For example, a hacker could:

- Intercept any data that you send or receive
- Gain access to your shared files
- Hijack your Internet connection — and use up your bandwidth or download limit

Internet Security tips — to help you protect your wireless network

Here are some simple steps you can take to protect your wireless network and router:

- **Avoid using the default password:**
It's easy for a hacker to find out the manufacturer's default password for your wireless router — and then use that password to access your wireless network. So it's wise to change the administrator password for your wireless router. When you're deciding on your new password, try to pick a complex series of numbers and letters — and try to avoid using a password that can be guessed easily.
- **Don't let your wireless device announce its presence:**
Switch off SSID (Service Set Identifier) broadcasting — to prevent your wireless device announcing its presence to the world.
- **Change your device's SSID name:**
Again, it's easy for a hacker to find out the manufacturer's default SSID name for your device — and then use that to locate your wireless network. Change the default SSID name of your device — and try to avoid using a name that can be guessed easily.
- **Encrypt your data:**
In your connection settings, make sure you enable encryption. If your device supports WPA encryption, use that — if not, use WEP encryption.

- **Protect against malware and Internet attacks:**

Make sure you install a rigorous anti-malware product on all of your computers and other devices. In order to keep your anti-malware protection up to date, select the automatic update option within the product.

6. CONCLUSION

Wireless environment limits the strength of encryption algorithms. Attacks of different types have proven WEP security provided by the 802.11 standard insecure. The WLAN industry has responded by creating WPA and 802.11i to address the issues in the long term.

Most of today's security requirements can be met with 802.11x, which provides a solution that is effective and has not yet been broken.

Funk, Meetinghouse, and Microsoft all offer an 802.11x client and server solutions that are available today and provide security that is adequate for enterprise applications. For really important data, avoidance or some type of overall encryption might be prudent.

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